

www.arseam.com

PALEOENVIRONMENTAL INTERPRETATION OF THE CAMPANIAN IN ENUGU SHALE OUTCROPING ALONG ENUGU –ONITSHA EXPRESS ROAD

Ugwueze, Charles ¹. Ihunda, Chigozi Eze ². Adiela, U.P ³.

^{1,2} Department of Geology, Port Harcourt, Nigeria, University of Port Harcourt, Nigeria

³ Department of Petroleum Engineering, Nigerian Agip Oil Company, Port Harcourt, Nigeria

ABSTRACT

Paleoenvironment analysis of the Campanian in Enugu Shale analyses had been carried out. The analysis aim to determine the age of the rock and paleoenvironment of deposition using diagnostic species of foraminifera recovered from the exposure include: Haplophragmoides sp, Ammabaculites sp, Quinqueloculina, , Miliammian fusca, and Ostracod, and also shell fragment . The Enugu Shale is an indication of decrease in sea level with high abundance of foraminifera which suggest a tidal to supertidal marine foreshore depositional environment.

Keyword: Foraminifera, Paleoenvironment, Biostartigraphy

1.1.INTRODUCTION

The Anambra basin is the western synclinal arm of the Abakaliki anticlinorium in the lower Benue Trough. (Burke *et al.*, 1972) said that It was formed after the Santonian tectonic pulse as a sub-basin on the basis from the differential subsidence of fault block of the Benue . These are formed as a failed arm of the triple junction at the time when the North and South Atlantic were created during the Jurassic . The search for oil and gas in the basin started in 1938 and since then over 40 oil exploration (Nwajide *et al.*, 1996). The study is aim at reconstruction of the environment of deposition using biofacies, lithofacies out biostratigraphic analysis of sampled shale. The study area is located in Aguabor community in Enugu North L.G.A between latitudes 6⁰00'N and 6⁰30'N of the equator and longitudes 7⁰20'E and 7⁰30'E. (Fig.1)

Outcropping along Enugu –Onitsha Express Road

Fig.1:Location Map showing sampled Locations

1.2.GEOLOGICAL AND STRATIGRAPHIC FRAMEWORK OF ANAMBRA BASIN

The Benue Trough of Nigeria is a rift basin in central West Africa that extends NNE-SSW for 150 km in width and about 800 km in length . The the northern limit is the southern boundary of the Chad Basin.. Compressional folding, producing over 100 anticlines and synclines (Benkhelil, 1989). Major deformation structures include the Obi syncline in the Middle Benue, and the Lamurde anticline and the Dadinya syncline . Trough. Following Mid-Santoniantectonism. The Anambra Basin is logical to include the Anambra Basin in the Benue Trough that is being a related structure that developed after the compressional stage.

1.3.METHODOLOGY

A total of five (5) samples obtain from an exposure in Enugu Shale within Aguabor community.These samples were processed and analyzed for planktic foraminifera using the standard micropaleontological. About 25g of samples were placed into the sample plates. The

samples had been dried on a particular hot plate at about 800⁰C for 1-2 hours. The sample plates were allowed to cool and weighed. The samples were washed with a special liquid soap and water . A four sieve mesh sizes of 500, 250, 150 and 63 microns were used and dried. Samples were labeled accordingly. Foraminifera were picked from the packaged samples and studied with the aid of a reflected light binocular Zeis microscope.

1.4.RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Lithostratigraphic Description: The lithostratigraphic outcrop sample has been shown that the min constituent of the lithofacies to be shale. They are from brown to dark grey in color. The shales are fine-grained. The accessories minerals present are profusion include ferruginous mica flakes , material and some shell fragments. The stereo binocular microscope has been used to describe the samples (Figure.2).

Figure.2: Lithologic Discription of the Study Area

Table.1. WET SIEVE ANALYSIS

Serial number	Depth (ft)	Original weight of sample(g)	Weight of paper	A	%	B	%	C	%	D	%
1	Top	25	0.6	7.8	31.2	1.4	5.6	0.8	3.2	15	66.4
2	1	25	0.6	9.8	39.2	1.0	4	0.1	0.4	14.1	56.4
3	2	25	0.6	11.6	46.4	0.2	0.8	0.1	0.4	13.1	52.4
4	3	25	0.6	13.9	55.6	0.6	2.4	0.1	0.4	10.4	41.6
5	Base	25	0.6	13.1	52.4	2.1	8.4			9.8	39.2

5 Sample were wet sieved to determine the percentage of sand, silt and clay ratio, the sample were also examined for their fossils content

1.5. BIOSTRATIGRAPHY

This is the differentiation and correlation of rock units on the basis of their fossil content. The foraminifera species recovered from the sample were shell fragment, Haplophragmoides sp., Ammobaculites sp, Miliammian fusca, Quinqueloculina. The foraminifera microfauna of the study area is predominantly of calcareous taxa. The micropaleontology distribution chart is as shown in Figure.3

Figure.3: Grain size ratio and Percentage Distribution of Foraminifera

1.6. DISCUSSIONS

From the Sedimentologic and micropaleontology analyses that were carried out, it is obvious that from the extensive terrestrial swamps of the sediment to extensive marine environment of the younger sediments. Most of the environmental interpretations here are mainly based on the affinities of certain microfauna. From sample analysis the presence of leaflet , rootlet, and some microfauna

Outcropping along Enugu –Onitsha Express Road

Fig 1,2,7 and 8. *Haplophragmoides* sp

Fig 9 *Ammobaculites* sp

Fig 4 and 5. Shell fragment

Fig 6 *Quinqueloculina*

Fig 10 Ostracod

phylum Mollusca include Shell fragment which shows a remarkable abundant within indicate tidal to supratidal which is marine foreshore environments setting, the fauna content from the base of Enugu Shale yielded *Haplophragmoides* sp., *Ammobaculites* sp, *Miliammian fusca*,

Quinqueloculina, *Ostracod*, and shell fragment. Abundant calcareous material such as root leaves, stems and leaflet; But however the vast majority live in normal marine habitat . The rock sample within these intervals are mainly of Shale.

Sample 1-2 shows a rootlet and leaflet and may indicate an infiltration of marine water/redeposition into the marine depositional environment. The rock samples within these intervals which is shale. The macro and microfauna phylum (Mollusca) include shell fragment and *Quinqueloculina*. Sample 3-4 shows abundant microfauna which means that the depositional environment is very favorable. But the presences of *Quinqueloculina* indicate a shallow marine environment.

1.7. PALAEOENVIRONMENT:

The preponderance shows that the environment was probably that of miner foreshore as exemplified by the lithologic sequence in the study area. It gave rise to the observed parallel sequences and fissile black shale overlain by an erosional base indicates deposition in a low energy environment below wave base and the absence of oxygen deficient bottom foraminifera assemblage; indicate that normal marine salinity prevailed during the deposition.

1.8. CONCLUSION

The paleoenvironmental study of the Enugu shale was based on the five outcrop shale samples. The sample yielded a reasonable palynomorphs .The present study indicates that the foraminifera analysis showed a standard method whereby it denotes a marine environment. The presence of microfauna *Haplophragmoides* sp., *Quinqueloculina*, *Ammobaculites* sp., *Miliammian fusca* is an indicative of occasional marine incursions.

REFERENCE

- Adegoke, O.S.Dessauvagie, T.F. J, Kogbe C.A. 1971. Planktonic Foraminifera in the Gulf of Gunea Sediments. Pp. 197-213
- Adegoke, O.S. 1969. Eocene stratigraphv of southern Nigeria.Colloquesur I Eocene, III. Bureau de Rechercheseologiqueset Minières 69. 22-48.
- Adeniran, B.V., 1997: Quantitative neogene planktic foraminifera biostratigraphy of western Niger delta. NAPE Bull vol.12 No.1 pg 54 – 59.

Outcropping along Enugu –Onitsha Express Road

- Agagu .O.K., (1981) Effect of overpressure in petroleum accumulation in the Niger subsurface. AAPG Bull Vol. 10 pg 50-75.
- Anyanwu, N.P.C., Arua, I., 1990. Ichnofossils from the Imo Formation and their palaeoenvironmental significance. Journal of Mining and Geology 26,1-4.
- Benkhelil, J., 1989. The origin and evolution of the Cretaceous Benue Trough (Nigeria). Journal of African Earth Sciences 8.251-282.
- Berggren, W.A., 1960. Paleocene biostratigraphy and planktonic foraminifera of Nigeria (West Africa). International Geological Congress, Copenhagen. Report 21 (6), 41-55.
- Boboye, O.A., and Adeleye, A.M 2009. High resolution biostratigraphy of early Pliocene – late Miocene calcareous nannoplanktons and foraminifera, Nigeria. European journal of scientific research vol. 34(3): pg308-325.
- Bolli, H. M., & Saunders, J. B. 1985. Oligocene to Holocene low latitude planktic foraminifera. In Bolli, H. M., Saunders, J. B., & Perch-Nielsen, K. (Eds), Plankton Stratigraphy, Cambridge Earth Sciences Series, Cambridge University Press, pp.165-262.
- Bullard, E.C., Everett, J.E., Smith, A.G., 1965. Fit of the continents around the Atlantic. Philosophical Transactions of the Royal Society London A 258, 41-51.
- Burke, K.C., Dessauvagie, T.F.J., Whiteman, A.J., 1972. Geological history of the Benue valley and adjacent areas. In: Dessauvagie. T.F.J., Whiteman, A.J. (Eds.), African Geology. University of Ibadan Press, Nigeria. pp. 187-218.
- Hosper 1971. The Geology of the Niger delta area. Great Britain Institute of Geological Science report. 70 (16) pg 42.
- King, L.C., 1950. Outline and disruption of Gondwanaland. Geological Magazine 87,353-359.
- Merki P.J., 1972. Structural geology of the Cenozoic Niger delta. Dessauvagie: T.F.J and Whiteman, A.J (eds). African Geology, University of Ibadan press pg 635-646.
- Murat, R.C., 1972. Stratigraphy and Paleogeography of the Cretaceous and Lower Tertiary in Southern Nigeria. In: Dessauvagie, T. F.T., Whiteman, A.J. (Eds.), African Geology. University of Ibadan Press, Nigeria, pp. 251-266.
- Nwachukwu, S. O., 1972. The tectonic evolution of the Southern portion of the Benue Trough, Nigeria. Geological magazine (109) pp.411-419.

- Nwajide, C.S., 1990. Cretaceous sedimentation and palaeogeography of the Central Benue Trough. In: Ofoegbu, C.O. (Ed.), The Benue Trough Structure and Evolution. Friedr.Vieweg and SohnBraunchweig/Wieshaclen, pp. 19-38.
- Obi, G.C., Okogbue, C.O., Nwajide.C.S. 2001. Evolution of the Enugu Cuesta: A tectonically driven erosional process. *Globa Journal of Pure Applied Sciences* 7., pp. 321-330.
- Ogbe F.G.A (1982) The biostratigraphy of the nigerdelta,Nigeria. *Journal of Minningand Geology*,18 (2):pg 545-582.
- Olade, M. A. 1975. Evolution of Nigeria's Benue Trough (Aulacogen): A tectonic Model, *Geological magazine*. (112) pp. 575-583.
- Reyment, R.A., 1965. In: *Aspects of the Geology of Nigeria*. University of Ibadan Press, Nigeria, pp. 145.
- Reyment R.A 1967 *Outline of geology of Nigeria*. University of Ibadam press, Ibadam, Nigeria 145.
- Short, K.C., Stauble, A.J., 1967. *Outline of geology of Niger delta*. American Association of Petroleum Geologists Bulletin 51, 76-779.
- White, E.I., 1926. Eocene fishes from Nigeria. *Bulletin of the Geological Survey of Nigeria* 10, 1-78.